

Oxidation of aliphatic amides by *N*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide in acid medium catalyzed by ruthenium(III) : a kinetic and mechanistic study

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The kinetics of the ruthenium(III)-catalyzed oxidation of urea and substituted ureas, namely, methylurea, ethylurea and propylurea by sodium *N*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide or chloramine-B (CAB) in HCl medium have been studied at 30°. The reaction rate shows a first order dependence each on [CAB], [amide] and [Ru^{III}] and fractional order on [H⁺]. Additions of halide ions and the reaction product of CAB (benzenesulfonamide) and the variation of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium do not have any significant effect on the reaction rate. Activation parameters have been evaluated. The rate increases in D₂O medium. Proton inventory studies were made in H₂O-D₂O mixtures for both the amides. A Taft linear free energy relationship is observed for the reaction with $\rho^{\ddagger} = -0.88$ and -3.20 and $\delta = -0.33$, indicating that electron-donating groups enhance the rate. An isokinetic relation is observed with $\beta = 372$ K confirmed by the Exner criterion. The protonation constant of monochloramine-B has been evaluated to be 8.6. A mechanism consistent with the observed kinetic data has been proposed. The rate of oxidation increases in the order : propylurea > ethylurea > methylurea > urea.

The chemistry of *N*-halogeno compounds has received considerable attention because of their application in reactions where selective and/or limited oxidations of compounds are required. Compounds in which *N*-halogen bond is attached to an aromatic moiety, generally known as organic *N*-haloamines, are stable and suitable as mild oxidants for a variety of reductants. The prominent member of this group chloramine-T (CAT) is well known as an analytical reagent for the determination of diverse substrates and mechanistic aspects of these reactions have been documented¹. The benzene analogue chloramine-B (C₆H₅SO₂NCINa. 1.5 H₂O; CAB) is becoming important as a mild oxidant² and the compound can be easily prepared from benzenesulfonamide and chlorine.

Amides are used as disinfectants and antiseptics. They are good reducing agents, plasticizers, solvents for synthesis and stabilizers for hypochlorite bleaches. A study of kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amides is a subject of importance from the point of understanding the nature and mode of cleavage of amide bond. The reactivity of amides depends on the nature of substituent on carbonyl carbon and amino nitrogen. A review of literature shows that although some amides have been oxidized, there is limited information on the oxidation of urea and substituted urea³. It was therefore of interest to investigate this possibility in order to understand the relative rates, mechanisms and structure-reactivity correlations by the introduction of dif-

ferent groups. It was found that the reactions of urea and substituted ureas by *N*-haloamines were sluggish under ordinary conditions. After examining several catalysts, we found that Ru^{III} is an excellent catalyst for the oxidation of substituted ureas. Therefore, in the present communication, we report the mechanistic and kinetic aspects of oxidation of unsubstituted and substituted ureas, namely, methylurea (Meu), ethylurea (Etu) and propylurea (Pru) by chloramine-B in the presence of HCl and ruthenium(III) chloride as catalyst at 30°. Attempt has been made to identify the most probable reactive species of the oxidant in aqueous acid medium. Taft linear free energy and isokinetic relationships were observed during the course of these investigations.

Results and Discussion

Under pseudo-first order conditions of [amide] >> [CAB] at constant [amide], [HCl], [RuCl₃] and temperature, plots of log [CAB] vs time were linear ($r > 0.9885$), indicating a first order dependence of the reaction rate on [CAB]. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k') are given in Table 1. Furthermore, the rate constant did not change with the change in [CAB]. Increase in [amide] increased the k' values (Table 1). Plots of log k' vs log [amide] were linear ($r > 0.9942$) with unit slopes, showing a first order dependence of the rate on [amide]. Further, plots of k' vs [amide] gave straight-lines ($r > 0.9935$) passing through the origin, confirming the first order dependence on [amide].

Table 1. Effect of variation of reactant concentrations on the reaction rate

[HCl] = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [RuCl₃] = 4.82×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, *l* = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 30°

10 ⁴ [CAB] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [amide] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ <i>k'</i> (s ⁻¹)			
		Urea	Meu	Etu	Pru
6.0	10.0	1.08	1.78	3.00	3.90
8.0	10.0	1.16	1.62	3.12	3.85
10.0	10.0	1.10	1.65	3.10	3.95
12.0	10.0	1.14	1.16	3.18	4.04
14.0	10.0	1.06	1.55	3.16	4.00
16.0	10.0	1.12	1.60	3.95	3.95
10.0	5.0	0.58	0.82	1.58	2.10
10.0	8.0	0.89	1.26	2.50	3.30
10.0	10.0	1.10	1.65	3.10	3.95
10.0	15.0	1.70	2.55	4.50	6.05
10.0	20.0	2.15	3.40	6.08	7.90
10.0	25.0	2.90	4.50	7.70	9.95

When the [HCl] was increased, the rate of reaction increased (Table 2) and the plots of log *k'* vs log [HCl] were linear (*r* > 0.9940) with fractional slopes (~0.60), indicating a fractional order dependence on [HCl]. The reaction rate increased with increase in [Ru^{III}] (Table 2), and plots of log *k'* vs log [Ru^{III}] were linear (*r* > 0.9918) with unit slopes, showing a first order dependence on [Ru^{III}]. Addition of Cl⁻ ion in the form of NaCl (0.1–0.6 mol dm⁻³) at constant [H⁺] (0.1 mol dm⁻³) did not affect the rate of reaction. Hence the dependence of the rate on [HCl] reflected the effect of [H⁺] only on the reaction. Similarly, addition of Br⁻ ion in the form of NaBr (5.0×10^{-4} – 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) had no effect on the rate.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [HCl] and [RuCl₃] on the reaction rate
 [CAB]₀ = 10.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [amide]₀ = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, *l* = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 30°

10 ² [HCl] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [RuCl ₃] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ <i>k'</i> (s ⁻¹)			
		Urea	Meu	Etu	Pru
2.0	4.82	0.36	0.57	1.98	2.80
5.0	4.82	0.70	1.15	1.98	2.40
10.0	4.82	1.10	1.75	3.10	3.95
15.0	4.82	1.40	2.30	3.90	5.00
20.0	4.82	1.68	2.72	4.60	5.90
25.0	4.82	1.92	3.15	5.15	6.60
10.0	1.96	0.45	0.62	1.15	1.40
10.0	2.52	0.61	0.86	1.52	1.96
10.0	3.64	0.85	1.24	2.25	2.75
10.0	4.82	1.10	1.65	3.10	3.95
10.0	7.24	1.85	2.55	4.78	6.18
10.0	9.26	2.52	3.35	6.25	8.10

Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulfonamide (5.0×10^{-4} – 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) or variation of ionic strength (0.2–1.0 mol dm⁻³) of the medium had no effect on the rate. The dielectric constant of the medium was varied by adding methanol (0–40%, v/v) to the reaction mixture, but the rates were not significantly altered. Blank experiments with methanol indicated that oxidation of methanol was negligible during the period of the experiment.

The reaction was studied with varying temperature (25–40°) and from the linear Arrhenius plots (*r* > 0.9895) of log *k'* vs 1/*T*, values of activation parameters for the overall reaction were computed (Table 3). As the rate dependent on [H⁺], solvent isotope studies in D₂O medium for urea and

Table 3. Activation parameters for the oxidation of amides by CAB in the presence of HCl and Ru^{III} catalyst

[CAB]₀ = 10.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [amide]₀ = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [RuCl₃] = 4.82×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, *l* = 0.8 mol dm⁻³

Amide	<i>E</i> _a kJ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>H</i> [#] kJ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> [#] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>G</i> [#] kJ m ⁻¹
Urea	63.2	60.7	-120.7	97.3
Meu	53.6	55.1	-149.0	96.2
Etu	47.3	44.7	-164.9	94.7
Pru	43.4	40.9	-172.7	94.0

methylurea revealed that while *k'* (H₂O) = 1.10×10^{-4} and 1.65×10^{-4} s⁻¹, *k'* (D₂O) = 1.75×10^{-4} and 2.50×10^{-4} s⁻¹, respectively. The solvent isotope effect *k'* (H₂O) / *k'* (D₂O) = 0.63 and 0.66 for the two amides. Proton inventory studies were made in H₂O–D₂O mixtures for both the amides and the results are shown in Table 4. Addition of an aqueous solution of acrylamide to the reaction mixture did not cause polymerization. This suggests the absence of free radical involvement during the oxidation.

Based on absorption spectra, Connick *et al.*⁴ showed that the octahedral complexes such as [RuCl₅(H₂O)]²⁻,

Table 4. Proton inventory studies for the oxidation of urea and methylurea in H₂O–D₂O mixtures

[CAB]₀ = 10.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [amide]₀ = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 10.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [RuCl₃] = 4.82×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, *l* = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 30°

Atom fraction of deuterium (<i>n</i>)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _{obs} ⁿ (s ⁻¹)	
	Urea	Meu
0.000	1.10	1.65
0.248	1.20	1.78
0.496	1.32	1.96
0.744	1.52	2.22
0.992	1.75	2.50

$[\text{RuCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2-}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$, $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$ and $[\text{RuCl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}$ do not exist in aqueous solutions of RuCl_3 . However, it has been shown that the following equilibrium exists for Ru^{III} in acidic solutions⁵,

Singh *et al.*⁶ used the above equilibrium in ruthenium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of primary alcohols by bromamine-T and of glycols by *N*-bromoacetamide in HClO_4 medium. In the present study, however, the zero effect of chloride ion on the rate indicates that the complex ion, $[\text{RuCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$, is assumed to be reactive catalyst species that interacts with the amide to form a complex intermediate.

Earlier workers⁷ showed the existence of similar equilibria in acid and alkaline solutions of *N*-metallo-*N*-haloarylsulfonamides. Chloramine-B ($\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCINa}$) like chloramine-T, behaves as a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions forming different species as shown in eqns. (2–6),

In acid medium, the probable oxidizing species are PhSO_2NHCl , $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2$, HOCl and H_2OCl^+ . The involvement of $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2$ in the mechanism leads to a second order rate law and negative effect of PhSO_2NH_2 according to eqn. (5), which is contrary to the experimental observations. As eqn. (4) indicates a slow hydrolysis, if HOCl were the primary oxidizing species, a first order retardation of the rate by the added PhSO_2NH_2 would be expected contrary to the experimental results. Hardy and Johnston⁸, who studied the pH-dependent relative concentrations of the species present in acidified chloramine-B solutions of comparable molarities, showed that PhSO_2NHCl is the likely oxidizing species in acid medium. Narayanan and Rao⁹ and Subhashini *et al.*¹⁰ reported that monohaloamines can be further protonated at pH 2, as shown in the following eqns. (7) and (8) for monochloramine-T or CAT ($p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NHCl}$) and monochloramine-B or CAB ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{NHCl}$), respectively,

The second protonation constants for CAT and CAB are 102 and $61 \pm 5 \text{ M}^{-1}$, respectively, at 25° . However, Gupta¹¹ believes that the values could be lower than those reported by the above workers^{9,10}.

In the present case, the fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ indicates that the protonation of PhSO_2NHCl results in the formation of $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+$ which is likely to be the active oxidizing species involved in the mechanism of the substrate(s). Based on the preceding discussion, a mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed for the reaction in acid medium. In Scheme 1, the Ru^{III} -S complex (X) reacts with the oxidant species, $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+$, in a slow step or the rate-determining step (rds) to form an intermediate complex (X') which then hydrolyzes to the end products.

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, S represents the amide substrates, while X and X' represent the complex intermediate species whose structures are shown in Scheme 2. A detailed mechanistic interpretation of the Ru^{III} -catalyzed amide-CAB reaction in acid medium is presented in Scheme 2. An initial equilibrium involves protonation of $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}$ forming the active oxidizing species of CAB, $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+$ (step (i) in Scheme 1, but not shown in Scheme 2). In the next fast pre-equilibrium, the nitrogen atom of the amide coordinates to the metal centre of the active catalyst species, $[\text{RuCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$, to form a loosely bound metal complex anion X (step (ii) of Scheme 2) trapped in a solvent cage. This kind of loose metal ion substrate complex formation has been used as an intermediate in some studies involving Ru^{III} catalyst⁶. Then an electrophilic attack by $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+$ at the amide nitrogen of X to form *N*-chloramide intermediate (X') through fast inter-molecular

Scheme 2

rearrangement, with the elimination of $PhSO_2NH_2$ and undergoes Hoffmann rearrangement which is followed by hydrolysis [step (iv) and (v)] to give the corresponding alkyhydrazines.

From the slow step of Scheme 1,

$$\text{Rate} = -d[CAB] / dt = k_3 [PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+] [X] \quad (9)$$

If $[CAB]_t$ represents the total effective concentration of CAB,

$$[CAB]_t = [PhSO_2NHCl] + [PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+] \quad (10)$$

By substituting for $[PhSO_2NHCl]$ from equilibrium step (i) of Scheme 1 in eqn. (10) one obtains,

$$[CAB]_t = \frac{[PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+]}{K_1[H^+]} + [PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+]$$

or

$$[CAB]_t = \frac{[PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+] \{K_1[H^+] + 1\}}{K_1[H^+]}$$

or

$$[PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+] = \frac{K_1[H^+][CAB]_t}{K_1[H^+] + 1} \quad (11)$$

By substituting for $[PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+]$ from eqn. (11) and for $[X]$ from equilibrium step (ii) into eqn. (9), the following rate law (eqn. 12) is obtained :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [CAB]_t [H^+] [S] [Ru^{III}]}{K_1 [H^+] + 1} \quad (12)$$

This rate law is agreement with the experimental results.

Since $\text{rate} = k' [CAB]_t$, eqn. (12) can be transformed into eqns. (13) and (14),

$$k' = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [S] [Ru^{III}] [H^+]}{K_1 [H^+] + 1} \quad (13)$$

$$1/k' = \frac{1}{K_2 k_3 [S] [Ru^{III}]} + \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [S] [Ru^{III}] [H^+]}$$

Based on eqn. (14), a plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[H^+]$ at constant [amide], $[Ru^{III}]$ and temperature was found to be linear ($r > 0.9860$) for each amide. Protonation constant K_1 or (K_p) of $PhSO_2NHCl$ and ($K_2 k_3$) values were calculated from the slope and intercept of these plots for the standard run with $[CAB]_0 = 10.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{amide}]_0 = 10.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[RuCl_3] = 4.82 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 30° . The calculated deprotonation constant, $K' = 1/K_1$, of $PhSO_2NHCl$, K_1 and ($K_2 k_3$) are presented in Table 5. The near constancy of K_1 and K' values forms a strong indirect evidence for the existence of the reactive species $PhSO_2NH_2Cl^+$ of the oxidant in acid medium, supporting the proposed mechanism of oxidation of amides by CAB (Scheme 1).

Table 5. Data calculated using equation (14)*

Amide	$k_2 k_3$ s^{-1}	K_1 or K_p $dm^{-3} \text{ mol}$	K' $dm^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Urea	51.9	8.3	0.12
Meu	98.8	6.5	0.15
Etu	129.7	9.8	0.10
Pru	172.9	9.9	0.11

* Calculated from a plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[H^+]$ (values of $[H^+]$ were taken from Table 2, i.e. variation of $[HCl]$). Experimental conditions are as in Table 2.

Scheme 1 is supported by the following experimental observation. (i) It is interesting to note that the rate in D_2O medium is faster than in H_2O , since D_3O^+ ion is a stronger¹² acid than H_3O^+ by a factor of 2 to 3, a solvent isotope effect of this magnitude is to be expected. But the observed inverse solvent isotope effect, $k'(D_2O) / k'(H_2O)$ is 1.59 and 1.52 for urea and methylurea. This probably shows that since the protonation step is followed by hydrolysis involving the O-H bond scission, the normal kinetic isotope effect $k_H / k_D > 1$ could counter balance the solvent isotope effect. The proton inventory studies made in H_2O - D_2O mixtures could throw light on the nature of the transition state. The dependence of the rate constant, k_{obs}^n on the deuterium atom fraction (n) in the solvent mixture is given by the following form of Gross-Butler equation¹³,

$$k_{\text{obs}}^0 / k_{\text{obs}}^n = \frac{\text{TS}}{\text{RS}} \frac{\pi(1-n+n\phi_i)}{\pi(1-n+n\phi_j)} \quad (15)$$

where ϕ_i and ϕ_j are isotopic fractionation factors for isotopically exchangeable hydrogen sites in the transition state (TS) and in the ground / reactant state (RS), respectively. The Gross-Butler equation (15) permits the evaluation of ϕ_i when the value of ϕ_j is known. However, the curvature of a proton inventory plots could reflect the number of exchangeable protons in the reactions¹³. Plots of k_{obs}^n vs n (Table 4) are curves in the present case; these in comparison with the standard curves indicate the involvement of a single proton or H-D exchange in the reaction sequence¹⁴. This proton exchange infers the participation of hydrogen in the formation of transition state.

(ii) The effect of varying solvent composition on the rate of reaction has been described in detail^{15,16}. For limiting case of zero angle approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole system, Amis¹⁶ showed that a plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/D$, gives a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between a negative ion and a dipole or between two dipoles, whereas a positive slope results for a positive ion-dipole interaction. The total absence of the effect of varying dielectric constant on the rate can not be explained by the Amis theory¹⁶. Applying the Born equation, Laidler derived the following for a dipole-dipole reaction,

$$\log k' = \ln k_0 + 3/8 kT (2/D - 1) \left\{ \frac{\mu_A^2}{r_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{r_B^3} - \frac{\mu_{\ddagger}^2}{r_{\ddagger}^3} \right\} \quad (16)$$

where k_0 is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant, μ the dipole moment and r the radii of the reactants and activated complex. It is seen that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant, when $r_{\ddagger}^3 > r_A^3 + r_B^3$. On the other hand, $r_{\ddagger}^3 \approx r_A^3 + r_B^3$ implies the absence of a dielectric constant on the rate, as was observed in the present investigations, signifying that the transition state is not very different from the reactants.

(iii) The existence of a Linear Free Energy Relationship (LFER) for the oxidation of amides by CAB has been evaluated¹⁷. Tests for the complete Taft equation as well as single parameter correlations with polar substituent constant σ^* , and steric substituent constant E_s were made by plotting $\log k'$ vs σ^* , $\log k'$ vs E_s , and $\log k' - E_s$ vs σ^* . The following equations were found :

$$\log k' = -0.88 \sigma^* - 3.60 \quad (r = 0.9050) \quad (17)$$

$$\log k' = -0.33 E_s - 3.62 \quad (r = 0.8434) \quad (18)$$

$$(\log k' - E_s) = -3.20 \sigma^* - 3.50 \quad (r = 0.9962) \quad (19)$$

The implication of the electronic effect on the rate is less clear from eqn. (17). The value of $\rho^* = -0.88$ suggests that the electronic effect plays a role in the reaction. The sensitivity towards the steric effect ($\delta = -0.33$) is not too significant as revealed by eqn. (18). However, an excellent correlation in eqn. (19) shows that both steric and electronic factors have a synergistic effect on the rate. The negative values of the reaction constant ρ^* (-0.88 and -3.20) indicate that the presence of the electron-donating group in the amide substrate increases the reaction rate. From the inspection of rate data, the rate of oxidation of amides follows the order : propyl > ethyl > methyl > urea.

(iv) It is seen from the Table 3 that the activation energy is highest for the slowest reaction, indicating that the reaction is enthalpy controlled. The activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the four amides are linearly ($r = 0.9914$) related by plotting ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger . From the slope, the value of isokinetic temperature (β) is computed as 375 K. Further verification of the isokinetic relation has been done by the Exner criterion¹⁸ by plotting $\log k'_{313\text{K}}$ vs $\log k'_{303\text{K}}$ which gives a straight-line ($r = 0.9928$). The value of β was calculated from the equation, $\beta = T_1(1-q)/(T_1/T_2) - q$, where q is the slope of the Exner plot; β was found to be 369 K. The values of β from the plots calculated are much higher than the experimental temperature (303 K) proved that the reaction is enthalpy-controlled. The moderate energy of activation supports the proposed mechanism while the constancy of ΔS^\ddagger values point out that the amides are oxidized by a similar mechanism. The fairly high negative ΔS^\ddagger values point towards the formation of a more ordered activated state from the reactants.

Experimental

Chloramine-B (CAB) was prepared as reported earlier¹⁹ and the purity was checked by iodometric titration and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy²⁰. An aqueous solution of the compound was prepared, standardized by the iodometric method and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration.

Urea, methylurea and ethylurea (Merck) were used as received. Propylurea was prepared²¹ and it was confirmed by its melting point. Fresh aqueous solutions of amides were prepared whenever required. Solution of RuCl₃ (Arora-Mathey) in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl was used as catalyst in acid medium. Allowance was made for the amount of HCl present in the catalyst solution for kinetic runs. The ionic strength of the system was maintained at a constant high value ($I = 0.8$ mol dm⁻³) using a concentrated solution of NaClO₄.

Solvent isotope studies were made with D₂O (99.4%) supplied by the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. Triple-distilled water was used for preparing all aqueous solutions.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ([substrate] >> [oxidant]) at constant temperature in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes coated black on the outside. The oxidant and the requisite amounts of substrate, NaClO₄, HCl and RuCl₃ solutions and water (for constant total volume) taken in separate boiling tubes were thermally equilibrated at 30°. The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of a measured amount of CAB to the mixture and then shaken intermittently for uniform concentration. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of unconsumed CAB in known aliquots (5 ml each) of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k'*) calculated from the linear plots of log [CAB] vs time were reproducible within ± 3–5%. Regression analysis of the experimental data was carried out on an EC-75 statistical calculator to obtain the regression coefficient, *r*.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Reaction mixtures containing [CAB] >> [amide] in the presence of 10.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ HCl and 4.82 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ RuCl₃ were equilibrated with occasional shaking at 30° for 24 h. The iodometric determination of unreacted CAB in the reaction mixture showed that one mole of CAB was consumed per mole of the amide,

where R = NH₂ for urea, CH₃NH for methylurea, C₂H₅NH for ethylurea and C₃H₇NH for propylurea. The reduction product of CAB, benzenesulfonamide (PhSO₂NH₂), was detected²² by TLC using light petroleum-chloroform-*n*-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) as the solvent system and iodine as the spray reagent (*R_f* = 0.88). The presence of hydrazines as oxidation products of the amides in the reaction mixture was detected by salicylaldehyde tests²³. The other product, CO₂ was detected by conventional lime water test.

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